

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CERTAIN TYPES OF TRANSPORT-RELATED INJURIES IN CHILDREN

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ANNOTATION

Today, road traffic injuries among young people have become a major component of the overall problem of road traffic accidents. Currently, the number of road traffic incidents and resulting car crashes is increasing significantly. The reasons for this are twofold: on one hand, there are objective factors such as the growing number of imported and domestically produced vehicles and the condition of roads in the country; on the other hand, there are subjective factors like the quality of driver training and discipline on the roads.

Key words: Damage to children; non-lethal transport injury.

Currently, road traffic injuries are a global problem. Despite ongoing efforts, there is no decrease in the frequency of traffic accidents worldwide. This is due to a significant increase in the number of vehicle owners and the growing demand for vehicles, coupled with lagging development of high-quality road infrastructure, increasing urban populations, especially in large cities, and their growing needs. According to approximate calculations based on statistical data provided by WHO member countries, traffic fatalities reach about 1.2 million people annually, while about 50 million people suffer serious injuries as a result of accidents, which is equivalent to the population of several megacities or even small countries. Childhood injuries are an integral part of the overall problem of road traffic injuries and road safety. Child mortality has not only humanitarian but also political significance for society and the state, as it affects the overall child mortality rate, which reflects the country's level of development and well-being.

The circumstances and mechanisms of injuries in children due to road accidents are quite diverse, with a wide spectrum of organ and system damage. The prognosis for children's condition depends on the speed and timeliness of the measures taken. However, the severity of patients' condition and the extent of injuries often complicate diagnosis and the work of medical personnel, especially at the pre-hospital and early hospital stages of medical care.

According to the nature of the circumstances of injury, it is possible to distinguish two groups of children with road trauma: the first - children injured as a result of an accident while inside a vehicle, and the second group - children injured as a result of being hit by a vehicle, i.e., "child pedestrians." In the first group, isolated craniocerebral trauma is more common in affected children. Less commonly, craniocerebral trauma is combined with injuries to the upper and lower extremities, pelvic bone fractures (traumas of the musculoskeletal system). And even more rarely, severe craniocerebral trauma is combined with injuries to internal organs. An injury received inside a vehicle is always a "whiplash" injury (damage to the neck due to its forced sharp extension with subsequent sharp flexion or vice versa). Based on the analysis of the first group of affected children, damage to one body segment is noted in up to 60% of cases, two body segments in up to 36% of cases, and three body segments in up to 4% of cases. Children in the first group most often have craniocerebral trauma - up

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to 60% of cases; combination of craniocerebral trauma with skeletal trauma (fractures of the musculoskeletal system) - up to 32% of cases, and combination of craniocerebral trauma, musculoskeletal trauma, and internal organ damage, internal bleeding - up to 8% of cases. The latter cases are already severe trauma; these are children with shock and are in the risk group. In the second group, children injured as a result of being hit by a vehicle still have more severe combined injuries: this is a severe craniocerebral injury combined with fractures of the upper and lower extremities, pelvic bones, spinal trauma, damage to internal organs, and internal bleeding. This group of children more often experiences pronounced shock. Children are in a state of sopor (deep suppression of consciousness with loss of voluntary and preserved reflex activity) or unconscious - coma. In the second group, damage to one body segment is noted in approximately 13% of cases, two segments in up to 50-52% of cases, three segments in up to 24% of cases, and four segments in about 12% of cases.

The application of the presented mechanism will differ for primary school-aged children and adolescents. In primary school age, this mechanism is only being established, so it is important to reinforce the sequence of all stages, paying special attention to identifying road situations as special, activating memory to recall specific rules, executing them precisely, and exiting the situation. Situation assessment should be conducted in general terms, focusing on the main, vital parameters. As a result, younger students should develop a conviction in strict adherence to traffic rules, reinforced by appropriate practical skills, through activating their need for safety. Since younger schoolchildren have a poorly developed sense of danger, special emphasis should be placed on the child's emotional sphere when forming this mechanism. On one hand, to develop a "sense of danger" on and near the road, it is necessary to moderately evoke a healthy sense of fear in the child to activate the need for safety. On the other hand, it is more important to foster a sense of success and satisfaction from their correct actions on the road. In adolescence, the stage of focusing attention requires significantly less time due to teenagers' increased capabilities and richer personal experience compared to younger schoolchildren, especially in cases of improperly formed behavioral patterns on the road. When adolescents have developed a mechanism for safe behavior on the road, it is necessary to use visual aids to remind them about possible ways to focus attention and the negative consequences of ignoring them. The situation assessment stage in adolescence requires more detailed consideration compared to other stages. Teenagers should be presented with as many options as possible for how road situations might develop, allowing for detailed analysis from the perspectives of all participants. To support the harmonious development of adolescents, particularly their emerging sense of maturity and self-esteem, they should be given the opportunity to view the situation through the eyes of all participants: pedestrians, drivers, etc. It is important that visual aids allow adolescents to predict the development of events and make decisions independently. It is at this stage that adolescents develop the ability to recognize their choices and take responsibility for them. These situations should be both realistic and challenging. The remaining stages of the presented mechanism in adolescence are carried out automatically. As a result, adolescents should develop a clear understanding that their choice is not between following or not following traffic rules, but between managing circumstances or submitting to them - in other words, being in control of their lives or not. **The purpose of this study** was to conduct a comparative analysis of injuries occurring in different variants of transport injuries.

Material and method. The objects of the study were the materials of forensic medical examinations in cases of transport injuries involving children in Tashkent city during 2017. A total of 124 expert

opinions on living persons were analyzed. Of these, in 60 cases, injuries were sustained from impacts with parts of a moving car, in 53 cases injuries occurred inside the car, and 11 cases involved motorcycle-related injuries.

Conclusion: A comparative analysis of injuries sustained by children in car accidents, as pedestrians hit by moving vehicles, and in accidents involving two-wheeled vehicles revealed that head and limb injuries occur in all types of incidents. However, fundamental differences were found in limb injuries caused by the specific mechanism of trauma. This allows, in cases where the circumstances of the injury are unknown, to determine the mechanism of injury formation and, consequently, to differentiate the conditions under which the injuries occurred.

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